

DEVELOPING READING SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

It is important to form students' reading skills in English, and it is appropriate to pay special attention to reading comprehension. This article discusses the methodology of formation and development of English reading comprehension skills among students of higher educational institutions.

Introduction.

Currently, there are many areas that determine the bright future of our country and ensure its strength. The higher education system is undoubtedly of special importance among them. Because the future of our nation and people is closely related to the fate of young specialists who are receiving higher education today. From the first years of our country's independence, the educational system has been implemented in order to ensure that people acquire knowledge in conditions corresponding to world standards, mature physically and spiritually, develop their abilities and talents, and form feelings of loyalty and self-sacrifice in their hearts. At the heart of the incomparable efforts is this noble goal embodied.

Today, learning a language helps to develop the communication and personality of learners of all ages and people in all areas of our lives. Knowledge of foreign languages can increase a person's perspective in areas such as translation and language learning.

In the modern world, where there is a great demand for the English language and for professionals who have mastered it well, comprehensive learning of it requires careful formation of all skills. In order to master English at or near the level of native speakers, teachers will have to organize exercises, tasks and lessons aimed at mastering all language skills in the educational process and play the role of a facilitator (*assistant*) rather than a traditional teacher in the language learning process. These language skills are:

1. *Listen and understand;*
2. *Speaking;*
3. *Reading;*
4. *Writing.*

Each of these skills is important in achieving the intended goal of language learning. Therefore, their mastery and development remains one of the necessary tasks of today.

It is permissible to pay attention to reading skills before developing reading comprehension. Reading means the process of perceiving speech information expressed in literal symbols and noticing its content [1]. Reading is reading a text with unfamiliar content based on familiar, partially unfamiliar language materials, obtaining information, understanding the content, and perceptual interpretation. Reading is a receptive form of communication. Reading is written speech, a type of speech activity for communication. Through reading, the student gets acquainted with the customs of the language, culture, life history of the country being studied. Reading is a source of information.

Nowadays, reading is not only a source of information. The use of proper phonetic, grammatical, lexical materials, graphics, orthography is mastered and constantly enriched with new vocabulary.

Reading skills are also a tool for teaching listening comprehension, speaking, writing, and writing.

Studying is based on educational and educational developmental goals. The main purpose of reading - the practical purpose - is to read in English and get familiar with the content, that is, to get information by reading.

Literature review.

There are the following goals and tasks of study skills in higher educational institutions: formation and development of the profession and qualification of teaching; before studying, students should be able to read original literature related to their specialty and to be able to read it for different purposes; to be able to use monolingual and bilingual dictionaries and important information; independent study.

Working on reading in practical English has meaning and mechanisms. By the content of working on reading, we understand what is taught in reading, what is worked on and what to teach them to do.

I.A. Gruzinskaya defines "Reading mechanism as the ability to correctly and quickly identify eye-catching text material with sound images, to pronounce fragments of the text with full sound and tone accuracy."

Research methodology and empirical analysis.

Reading mechanisms include: characters; letters; letter combinations; words; sentences and pronounce and read them; rhythm; tone; memory; perception; anticipation-precognition; understand; speeds.

Now the psycho-physiological mechanisms of reading have been identified and the senses of sight, writing, speech and movement are being introduced into it. They participate in speech activities together and provide information while studying. Representation of content is carried out through reading mechanisms.

When reading and understanding an English text, 2 processes occur [4]:

- 1) *Reception;*
- 2) *Understanding.*

Humans have two signaling systems. The first signal comes to action as a result of the influence of objects, as a result of the influence of objects, the object looks on the basis of stimuli, the second signal system is triggered on the basis of word stimuli (on the basis of observation with the influence of words). Therefore, perception is the first signal system and understanding

is the second signal system. Perception is emotional, perception is the limited work of the first signal system, and understanding is the conscious reception. This is the conditioned work of the second signal system, and understanding is the conscious reception. This is the conditioned work of the second signal system. The second signal system can perform its task (function) only on the basis of the first signal system, and the second cannot be performed without the first. Pronouncing the text correctly without understanding its content is not reading. is able to form a process by properly connecting with it.

While studying practical English, we should consider the following methodological methods. In the language higher education institution, studies in practical English are worked on, reading is developed. In secondary school, reading is taught, it is founded, students have an understanding of reading.

Results.

Work on reading skills is put in the pedagogical professional direction, together with the development of reading, pedagogical professional skills are formed.

According to the reading technique, reading technique, understanding of the content of what is read is taught, it is developed.

Several methods were used to teach reading techniques.

1. The phonic method — phonic method. First, sounds are shown, then a graphic (symbol) - a letter representing a writing symbol is shown and taught. This method is also called the method of Z. M. Tsvetkova [2].
2. The word method - the teaching technique is taught by reading the whole word and teaching it back.
3. The sentence method - the technique of reading is taught by reading the sentence and teaching it back. This method S.K. Folomkina it is also called the and Kaar method.
4. Now the analytical-synthetic method is also used when working on teaching reading techniques.

As we all know, before the introduction of the Presett program in higher educational institutions, the teacher had the opportunity to ask and answer questions about the text in the Uzbek language based on the environment. However, the teaching process in modern higher educational institutions must be conducted strictly in English.

In order to achieve great results in teaching English, it is necessary to create a full English language environment in the auditoriums of the higher educational institution, that is, to explain the read text in full English, and to conduct questions and answers about the text by the teacher must be conducted entirely in English. It is appropriate for a teacher to choose a text in the process of teaching reading, taking into account the level of education, age, and level of education of a student of a higher educational institution.

Conclusion.

Teaching reading comprehension should be considered as teaching a type of speech activity. When this rule is taken into account, students are given the correct study guide. One of the methodical mistakes observed in the experiment, it is recommended to turn the language material into a material for use in the text activity instead of making it the sole educational task of mastering the language material or speaking close to the text. The primary final goal of teaching students of higher educational institutions to learn information by reading the text

should be put into practice. This is achieved only by performing speech acts, in this process it is intended to achieve a certain result, to learn the content, to acquire information. Reading the text is an educational-methodical activity aimed at spiritual enrichment and acquisition of new information. By using the methods mentioned above, the use of reading teaching exercises in the course of the lesson will greatly help to develop speaking skills.

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